

Charity and Christ-Like Service

There are several benefits to being charitable. The word charity is linked to kindness and the willingness to do good. Charity can encourage us to perform the best deeds and act reasonably and always better, according to the right reason chosen from an intellectual disposition called prudence, responsible for unifying knowledge and action. Cultivating a life with charity can help us develop patience, love, and empathy. Therefore, we can apply these attributes in different positive and adverse circumstances.

Surrounding myself with friends with the same perspective and following the same principles encourages me to have more charity with others. One of the reasons is that we often imitate those around us and are influenced by the habits and preferences of a social group. Furthermore, it is essential to surround ourselves with people with the same determination to achieve specific goals and behave in a particular way. As a temple worker, I have been able to help sisters in need of translation or guidance inside the temple. I remember one time a sister from Brazil was lost and didn't know where to go to do proxy sealing. She didn't speak English, and I didn't speak Portuguese, but I wanted to help her get to the correct place and receive a language card so her experience and temple would have been better. Therefore, I approached the sister and tried to assist her the best as I could. We were able to communicate by mixing English and Portuguese. Her face changed from worry to happiness. It was a fantastic experience for both of us.

Reading about the examples of Jesus Christ's love and charity made me ponder the importance of being kind to families, friends, colleagues, and people in general. This can sound like a simple concept, but being charitable can require us to be aware of our surroundings and be in tune with the Holy Ghost. I work in customer service and have a couple of experiences about

how hard it is to have charity when others are not kind. These experiences have helped me to ponder my efforts to achieve my goals and assist customers. Once, a bishop called my department, and I was trying to help them follow the instructions and policies correctly. Still, he was requesting things that were not aligned with the organization's policies. It is hard to be kind and charitable with things that are not up to us to decide, and leaders don't understand it, and they are rude to us. I explained that we couldn't do anything in that case because it didn't follow the church's instructions. I was charitable by explaining the situation with kindness and respect.

I was also thinking about a charitable person from the scriptures. I thought about Ruth because even though she was having a difficult time when her husband died, she chose to persevere and adapt to the changes she was having. Also, she could carry on to the end and never separated from the only person she had left, her mother-in-law. When the Heavenly Father sees our efforts to be charitable, He provides more blessings in our lives. Ruth followed her kind heart and returned with his mother-in-law to Bethlehem. Although new in this place, she was diligent and adaptable to finding work. I think I can follow her example by remembering that our value charity can bless other's lives. When we must live in unpleasant situations, we react in different ways. Ruth made a charitable decision by staying with her mother-in-law and working better days for both. Despite her pain, Ruth was a determined and persevering woman who decided to leave her old life behind and assist her mother-in-law.

Resources

<https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org/study/manual/old-testament-stories-2022/ruth-and-naomi?lang=eng>

<https://www.ldsiving.com/what-ruth-and-naomi-can-teach-us-about-sisterhood-and-friendship/s/10731>